

Geometrical Realization of Contact Angle Hysteresis for Multiphase DNS using PLIC

David Gösele*
University of
Stuttgart

Jonathan Wurst
University of
Stuttgart

Mathis Fricke
Technical University of
Darmstadt

Kathrin Schulte
University of
Stuttgart

An algorithm is developed [1] to model contact angle hysteresis for 3D multiphase DNS using Piecewise Linear Interface Calculation (PLIC). The basic features are adopted from [2], where the PLIC surface motion is geometrically restricted to a rotation around the contact line. An advection test (Couette flow, Figure 1a) shows, that the PLIC surfaces indeed follow this restriction, resulting in an exactly pinned discrete contact line. The numerical slip is reduced to zero. However, the contact angle deviates significantly from the analytical solution (as depicted in Figure 1b) and mesh refinement fails to rectify this discrepancy. To address this issue, we introduce a novel flux calculation for the volume fraction. Unlike the previous constant velocity assumption (Figure 2a), the new approach incorporates a linear velocity profile within the cells with vanishing velocity at the wall (Figure 2b). With this local velocity profile, the movement of the PLIC surface inside a cell follows a rotation around the contact line and is therefore locally consistent with contact angle hysteresis. As shown in Figure 1c, the combination of the contact angle hysteresis algorithm and the new flux calculation results in correct rotation for the advection test. Finally, the algorithm is used to simulate a deflected droplet pinned on a surface, and the resulting droplet oscillation frequency corresponds well with literature. It should be noted, however, that the new flux calculation has only a minor impact on the oscillation frequency.

References

- [1] D. Gösele, *Implementierung und Validierung eines Modells zur Beschreibung der Kontaktwinkel-hysteresis*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10069555>, 2023.
- [2] C. Fang, C. Hidrovo, F. Wang, J. Eaton, K. Goodson, *3-D numerical simulation of contact angle hysteresis for microscale two phase flow*, *Int. Journal of Multiphase Flow*, **34**, pp. 690–705, 2008.

*Email: david.goesele@itlr.uni-stuttgart.de

(a) Imposed velocity field.

(b) Standard flux calculation.

(c) New flux calculation.

Figure 1: Couette flow. Surface is initialized with a contact angle of 90° and advected with velocity field (a). CL is the contact line, the black lines are the calculated PLIC surfaces, the analytical solution of the fluid distribution is shown in blue.

(a) Standard flux calculation.

(b) New flux calculation.

Figure 2: Comparison of flux calculations in one exemplary cell. CL is the contact line. The PLIC surface is shown in blue, the velocity in red, the advected volume fraction in yellow.